

Three days after the bombardment, filter discs with overlaying cells were transferred to the petri dishes containing 25 ml MS2.5 medium supplemented with 8 mg L⁻¹ ammonium glufosinate for selecting transformed calli. These filters were transferred every 10 d onto the fresh selection medium. Petri dishes were always sealed with the parafilm and incubated at 26 °C in the dark. After 30-40 d, the new calli showing active cell proliferation on the selection medium and growing up about 1.0 cm diameters (referred to as resistant calli), were transferred to the MS-based regeneration medium containing maltose (30 g L⁻¹), kinetin (2.0 mg L⁻¹), *a*-naphthalene acetic acid [NAA] (0.5 mg L⁻¹), ammonium glufosinate (5.0 mg L⁻¹); the medium was solidified with 1.0% agarose. For plant regeneration, cultures were incubated at 26 °C in the dark for 2 wk and then transferred to light (55 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, daylight fluorescent tubes, 16-h photoperiod). After 4 wk, these calli were transferred onto regeneration medium with lower concentrations of agarose (0.5%, w / v) and ammonium glufosinate (3 mg L⁻¹). Regenerated shoots were transferred to the rooting medium (0.25%, w/v phytigel-

solidified MS medium with 1.5 mg NAA L⁻¹) and 4 wk later, they were transferred to pots in the greenhouse.

This new procedure produced an average of 510-684 transient transformants and 24-103 transformed AG^R calli per filter; the number of transformants was higher using gold particles and with pT_{Wa} plasmid (see table). Water stress created by using higher agarose concentration (1.0% instead of 0.5%) promoted somatic embryogenesis, and shoot regeneration frequencies of 69-91% were obtained from AG^R calli. A total of 235 plants obtained after transformation with the two plasmids were analyzed by PCR using a suitable set of primers derived from the promoter, *bar* or *PIN2* gene sequences. As an internal control, a set of primers that amplify a 304-bp product during PCR from *Act1* promoter region was used. Of these, 188 plants showed the amplification of expected size of DNA fragment, indicating that 80% of selected AG^R plants are true transgenic plants. All the transformed plants transferred to the greenhouse were fertile and showed good seed set within 110-145 d after planting. Further molecular and progeny analyses of these transgenic plants are in progress.

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Genetic analysis of a d1 chimeric rice plant

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A chimeric rice plant has been maintained through seed for more than 50 yr in our laboratory. It has both normal and dwarf tillers. The dwarf tillers have wide dark green leaves, short panicles, and small round grains. Differences in chimeric manifestations were observed in chimeric plants (see figure). Both the dwarf-type progenies and dwarf tillers of the chimeric plant

are short, with wide dark green leaves, short panicles, and small round grains. These characters are almost the same as the Daikoku dwarf carrying the *d1* gene. We therefore call the chimeric plants d1 chimeric type.

Progenies of both the dwarf and normal tillers of the chimeric plant were dwarf, chimeric, or normal (see figure). To test the inheritance of the chimeric expression, dwarf and normal plants obtained from chimeric plants were crossed. The 26 F₁ hybrids produced by crossing a dwarf plant with a normal plant were all normal. Furthermore, 18 and 34 F₁ hybrids from crosses of dwarf and normal tillers of chimeric plants with IR24 and Taichung 65 were all normal. Segregation in F₂ from the

reciprocal crosses of the dwarf plants with IR24, Taichung 65, and the normal plant segregated into 3 normal:1 dwarf (see table). The results indicate a single recessive gene controls chimeric expression of the d1 chimeric plant.

To test for allelism between d1 and the d1 chimeric plants, dwarf plants obtained from the chimeric plant were crossed to a genetic marker carrying the *d1* gene. Seventeen F₁ hybrids from the reciprocal crosses of *d1*/dwarf plant were all *d1*-like plants, indicating that chimeric locus is allelic to the *d1* locus.

High frequency mutation at the *d1* locus could cause the occurrence of a d1 chimeric plant. When the three types of progenies from the plant were selfed, the average frequency of chimeric type

Differences in chimeric manifestations: a) almost all tillers are dwarf type with few normal tillers, b) half the tillers are dwarf, the other half normal, and c) almost all the tillers are normal with few dwarf tillers.

Phenotypes of the progenies derived from chimeric plants: d) dwarf type, e) chimeric type having both dwarf and normal tillers, and f) normal type.

F₂ segregation for plant types in the crosses involving d1 chimeric plant.^a

Cross	Segregation in F ₂				χ ²	P
	Normal	Dwarf	Chimera	Total		
Dwarf plant/IR24	47	15	0	62	0.022	0.70-0.90
IR24/dwarf plant	224	71	3	298	0.137	0.70-0.90
Dwarf plant/TC65	260	88	0	348	0.015	0.90-0.99
TC65/dwarf plant	318	94	5	417	1.049	0.30-0.50
Dwarf plant/normal plant	383	134	3	520	0.233	0.50-0.70
Normal plant/dwarf plant	259	102	0	361	2.040	0.10-0.30

^aDwarf plant = dwarf plant progenies derived from d1 chimeric rice. Normal plant = normal plant progenies derived from d1 chimeric rice. ^bN = normal, D = dwarf.

from dwarf, chimeric, and normal types were 26.7, 44.4, and 9.8%, respectively. The frequency of mutation in dwarf to normal is higher than in normal to dwarf.

Based on the results obtained from the inheritance and allelic tests, dwarf plant progenies of chimeric plants have

the *d-1* alleles while the normal progenies have the wild *D-1* alleles. We hypothesize that originally the chimeric plant had the *D-1* allele, but then the gene mutated to the recessive *d-1* allele. As a result, a chimeric plant has both dwarf (*d-1* allele) and normal tillers (*D-1* allele). If the progenies of a chi-

meric plant inherited the *d-1* allele, they become dwarf plants. If progenies inherited the *D-1* allele, they become normal plants. Throughout the growth stages of the rice plant, the *d-1* allele may revert to *D-1* allele or vice versa causing a dwarf plant to produce normal tillers and a normal plant to have dwarf tillers.

We also hypothesize that the *dl* chimeric rice plant, a very unstable mutant, occurs due to the on and off expression of the *D-1* allele, which appears to be controlled by factors such as a mutable gene, transposons, and methylation. A fine restriction fragment length polymorphism linkage map for *dl* is being developed, and we are cloning the *dl* gene to understand the mechanism of high mutation in the d1 chimeric rice plant. ■

Increasing yield potential of irrigated rice through recurrent selection

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Recurrent selection allows scientists to increase the frequency of favorable genotypes from a large population

through selecting and intermating generations quickly.

To assess the possibility of using this breeding method in irrigated rice in Brazil, we divided 162 S_{0.2} families (S₀ plant-derived families self-pollinated twice) into two groups (early-maturing and medium-maturing) and evaluated them in two environments. Each group was divided into two subgroups and then tested in the field with controls BR-IRGA 409 (early-maturing) and CICA 8 (medium-maturing).

The experiment was laid out in two triple-square lattices (10 × 10 m and 8 × 8 m). The S_{0.2} families came from the early-maturing population CNA-IRAT 4PR/1/1 and medium-maturing population CNA-IRAT 4ME/1/1. Individual and joint analyses of variance were done; we also estimated variance components within each maturation cycle group.

In all cases, the F test revealed highly significant differences (P<0.01) among the mean grain yields for the early- and